

THERMOGRAPHIC NDE-
HYSTERESIS HEAT GENERATION IN POLYMERIC COMPOSITES

D.W. Wilson R.B. Pipes

M.D. Greenberg

Center for Composite Materials
University of Delaware
Newark, DE 19711

The hysteresis heat generation in polymeric composites during cyclic loading results in surface temperature distributions readily mapped by thermographic techniques. Stress concentration induced by defects cause corresponding increases in the surface temperature of the composite, indicating a relationship between heat generation and local state of stress. The use of thermography in NDE is based upon this relationship between defect induced stress and heat generation. If thermography is to be effectively used in a quantitative rather than qualitative manner for NDE of composites to locate subsurface flaws, the relationship between heat generation, stress field, and the resulting heat conduction through the laminate must be investigated.

An analytical model relating hysteresis heat generation to the state of stress within a lamina of arbitrary fiber orientation has been developed. This model relates lamina surface temperature to the maximum shear stress within the polymeric matrix phase, the loading frequency, and the viscoelastic properties of the material. The model is based upon the Kelvin-Voigt model of viscoelasticity and assumes uniform heat generation throughout the lamina.

Off-axis tensile tests were conducted with Scotchply 1002 Glass-Epoxy composite material. The transient and equilibrium temperature responses were monitored for fiber orientations of 0°, 15°, 30°, 45°, 60°, 75°, and 90° under tension-tension loading conditions at frequencies of 20Hz and 30Hz. The viscous response was determined for each fiber orientation by measuring the phase lag σ between the applied loading and material response, and the hysteresis loss per cycle.

SESSION 14:
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ANALYSIS, TEST AND PREVENTION-III

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J.G. Morley
Wolfson Institute of Interfacial Technology
University of Nottingham
Nottingham, NG7 2RD, United Kingdom

CO-CHAIRMAN:

J.A. Comie
Metal Matrix Composites
Advanced Composite Products Division
2 Lowell Industrial Park
Lowell, MA 01851

